

Formation Constants of Thallium(III) with Fumaric, Maleic and Phthalic Acids

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Manuscript received 21 February 1984, accepted 3 May 1984

The complexation of Tl^{III} with fumaric, maleic and phthalic acids are studied by the help of pH-metric data obtained at pH 2.0-3.5 and $\mu=0.1$ ($H^+ + Na^+$) ClO_4^- . 1 : 1 metal to ligand complexes are detected and their conditional formation constants are $\log K=4.45, 4.90$ and 5.65 , respectively. The possibility of the existence of hydroxo and protonated complexes in solution is discussed. The 1 : 1 complexes with fumarate and phthalate are supported by conductometric titrations whereas maleate gives 1 : 3 metal to ligand complex.

COMPLEXES of phthalic¹⁻⁴, maleic⁵⁻⁸ and fumaric⁹⁻¹¹ acids with a number of metal ions have been investigated mostly by potentiometric method. Complexes of thallium(III) with these acids have not been described earlier. It was hoped that these acids would react with Tl^{III} ions in solution to form complexes. The present investigation is aimed to determine the stability constants of Tl^{III} with these acids.

Experimental

0.05M Fumaric, 0.1M maleic and 0.03M phthalic acids (c.p. grade) were prepared in double distilled water. The acids were standardised by titration with standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution. 0.02M Thallic chloride solution (c.p., Mallinkrodt) was prepared using double distilled water and the solution was checked iodometrically. Other chemicals were prepared from c.p. products.

Potentiometric titrations of the acid alone (H_2L) and of the metal to ligand ratios 1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 6 and 1 : 8 were carried out at 25° in a jacketed beaker, continuously flushed with nitrogen gas during titration with 0.980N sodium hydroxide solution. The following mixtures were titrated (50 ml each) ;

(A) 0.02M $HClO_4$ + 0.08M $NaClO_4$,

(B) Mixture (A) + 0.02M acid,

(C) Mixture (B) + 0.0025, 0.0033, 0.005 or 0.01M Tl^{III} solution.

A Radiometer pH-meter type WGPYE model 290 fitted with combined glass and calomel electrodes was used to measure the pH. Conductometric titrations were performed by titrating 50 ml, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Tl^{III} solution with $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ acid. The conductance values were corrected for dilution and then plotted against the volume of the acid (ligand) added.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric titrations: The representative curves shown in Fig. 1 indicates that the metal-ligand titration curve C is well separated from the ligand titration curve B, and thus the liberation of protons is due to complexation. Consideration of the moles of alkali/mole of thallic ion indicates that single proton is replaced by thallic ion. Separation of solid phase was observed above pH 4.4 due precipitation of hydroxo species.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves : (A) 0.02 M $HClO_4$ + 0.08 M $NaClO_4$; (B) Mixture (A) + 0.02 M phthalic acid ; (C) Mixture (B) + 0.005 M Tl^{III} solution.

The calculations of the proton-ligand and the metal-ligand formation constants were made by using the method of interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ and half $\bar{n}$ values, respectively as adopted by Irving and Rossotti^{1,2}. Calculations of proton-ligand stability constants were carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}_A$

(average number of H^+ ions attached per ligand) against pH . The first and the second protonation constants corresponding to $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and $\bar{n}_A=1.5$, respectively were obtained from the curve. Table 1

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANT OF FUMARATE, MALEATE AND PHTHALATE AT 25° AND $\mu=0.1 M$

	Fumarate	Maleate	Phthalate
$\log K_1^H$	4.25	5.80	5.25
$\log K_2^H$	3.10	1.95	3.00

represents the protonation constants of the acids and these values agree quite well with those reported in the literature for fumaric⁹, maleic⁵ and phthalic⁶ acids.

From the titration curves using solutions B and C, $\bar{n}$ (average number of ligand molecules attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent) values were calculated in the pH range 2.0-3.5. The $\bar{n}$ values are plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curve of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves the values of stability constants, $\log k_1$, were determined. The conditional stability constants are recorded in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of Tl^{III} phthalic acid system: (a) 1 : 4 (0.01 M acid); (b) 1 : 2, (c) 1 : 4, (d) 1 : 6, metal to ligand ratio (0.02 M acid).

TABLE 2—THALLIUM(III) LIGAND LOG CONDITIONAL FORMATION CONSTANTS OF FUMARATE, MALEATE AND PHTHALATE AT 25° AND $\mu=0.1 M$

Tl^{III}/L	Fumarate	Maleate	Phthalate
1/2	4.70	4.94	5.30
1/4	4.22	4.88	5.70
(1/4)*	4.90	5.00	5.95
1/6	4.00	4.85	5.80
1/8	4.70	5.00	5.80

* Total concentration of the ligand = 0.01 M , others = 0.02 M .

Tl^{III} in aqueous perchloric acid solution exists¹³ as Tl^{3+} and its hydrolysed form $Tl(OH)^{2+}$, and $Tl(OH)^+$. For this reason, the data obtained above pH 3.5 are rejected due to the hydrolysis of Tl^{3+} . Consequently $\bar{n}$ values ≥ 1 are not included in Fig. 2 and only the 1 : 1 complexes are considered.

When the concentration of the acid is kept constant *viz.*, 0.02 M and the metal concentration is varied from 1 : 2 to 1 : 8 metal to ligand ratios, the conditional formation constants are nearly the same. This indicates that polynuclear complexes are not formed. The same conclusion is obtained by changing the acid concentration to 0.01 M as indicated from the experiments performed with 1 : 4 metal to ligand ratio (Table 2).

The formation of hydrolysed species e.g., $Tl(OH)L$ may occur in the solution due to the hydrolysis of Tl^{III} salts. Moreover, the hydrogenated ligand *i.e.*, HL^- may be involved in the reaction especially at low pH values where the concentration of L^{2-} is small and the first protonation constant is large. It has been found that protonated ligands such as nitrilotriacetate¹⁴ and acetate¹⁵ are complexed with Tl^{III} ions.

Conductometric titration: In order to confirm the stoichiometry of the complexes, conductometric titration experiments were carried out and the results are shown in Fig. 3. It is obvious that the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 1 for the Tl^{III} complexes of phthalate and fumarate. However, 1 : 3 metal

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration of 50 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tl^{III} solution with $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ acid: (a) fumaric, (b) maleic, (c) phthalic acid.

to ligand could be detected at higher concentrations of fumaric and phthalic acids. In the Tl^{III} -maleic acid system, only the ratio 1 : 3 metal to ligand is formed.

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